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Deliverable D3

Good practice guide for voltage generation of power frequency quantity, up to 36 kV for AC and 50 kV for DC, with superimposed frequency components up to 150 kHz

INRIM

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Glossary

AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
MV	Medium Voltage
EPM	European Partnership on Metrology
NMIs	National Metrology Institutes
VT	Voltage Transformer
DUT	Device Under Test
AWG	Arbitrary Waveform Generator
DAQ	Data Acquisition System / Module
UD	Universal Divider
HF	High Frequency
HV	High Voltage
RMS	Root Mean Square
RC	Resistor-Capacitor (circuit or divider)
LNE	Laboratoire National de Métrologie et d'Essais (France)
FFII	Fundación para la Investigación y el Desarrollo de la Industria (Spain)
INRIM	Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (Italy)
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
UNICAMPANIA	University of Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli" (Italy)
VSL	VSL Dutch Metrology Institute (Netherlands)
MSO	Mixed Signal Oscilloscope
PFG	Power Frequency Generator
RCVD	Resistive-Capacitive Voltage Divider
SF	Scale Factor
SFS	Sinusoidal Frequency Sweep
PXI	PCI eXtensions for Instrumentation
PLL	Phase Locked Loop
LFRD	Low Frequency Reference Device
HFRD	High Frequency Reference Device
LVD	Low Voltage Divider
LFA	Low Frequency Amplifier
HFA	High Frequency Amplifier
HFVT	High-Frequency Voltage Transformer

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1 Summary

This Good Practice Guide focuses on the development and characterization of advanced voltage generators for the testing of medium-voltage instrument transformers under supraharmonic conditions. The work addresses the need for accurate and reproducible test waveforms beyond the fundamental 50/60 Hz, covering the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range and reaching voltage levels up to 50 kV DC and 3 kV AC.

Several generator architectures have been designed and validated, each offering specific advantages. A series-connected generator with cascaded transformers provided robustness and high-voltage insulation, while a simplified generator using a single transformer enabled easier implementation with reduced complexity. A parallel-connected generator allowed flexible waveform superposition with reduced interaction between sources. An improved DC generator with ground-referenced harmonic injection simplified insulation requirements and achieved up to 1 kVRMS superimposed on 50 kV DC. Finally, a transient voltage generator based on an RLC discharge circuit reproduced damped sinusoidal oscillations up to 3 kV, simulating realistic high-frequency overvoltages.

Together, these solutions establish a versatile test infrastructure for calibration and performance assessment of instrument transformers, supporting both metrological research and future standardization in the field of power quality and high-frequency phenomena.

2 Introduction

One of the most urgent needs in power quality control of medium voltage instruments is to develop advanced voltage generation systems capable of producing AC and DC high voltage waveforms with superimposed frequency components representative of real world grid disturbances [1–2]. To properly evaluate voltage transformers under realistic operating conditions, especially those installed in medium voltage networks where harmonic disturbances in the 9 kHz–150 kHz band are increasingly present. It is crucial to generate voltage waveforms that closely replicate those found in actual grids. However, facilities capable of generating such voltages in a controlled, stable, and traceable manner up to 150 kHz are currently very limited. Even among leading National Metrology Institutes (NMIs), most voltage generation systems remain restricted to frequencies below 9 kHz [4]. Similarly, commercial high-voltage amplifier systems available on the market often fall short of the performance requirements necessary for precise VT characterisation.

As a result, validated and stable generation systems have become a critical component of modern test setups. The ability to reproduce realistic AC and DC voltage waveforms with accurately controlled spectral content up to 150 kHz is indispensable for the evaluation of voltage-dependent devices, such as VTs, insulators, and other power system components, under high frequency disturbances.

The ADMIT project [5] addresses this technological gap by developing and validating several complementary generator architectures:

- Chapter 2 describes the parallel-connected generator for AC.
- Chapter 3 describes the series connected generator for AC.
- Chapter 4 presents a method using a single transformer for AC, a simplified architecture offering easier implementation.
- Chapter 5 details the series-connected generator for DC.
- Chapter 6 introduces a transient voltage generator for DC.

Together, these systems enable the production of AC voltages up to 36 kV, DC voltages up to 50 kV, and controlled superimposed components with amplitudes up to 500 V in the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range. This represents a significant step forward, empowering NMIs to provide new calibration capabilities and extending traceability into a frequency range of growing importance for modern electrical networks.

The architecture and implementation of these generation systems, along with associated design considerations and traceability chains, are presented in this Good Practice Guide, which offers technical guidance for their application in both industrial and metrological environments.

3 Parallel-Connected Generators for AC Voltage at LNE

3.1 Introduction

This section describes a parallel-connected generator architecture developed to supply composite AC test voltages for the characterization of voltage transformers. The system combines two independent sources: one dedicated to generating the fundamental power frequency (50/60 Hz), and another providing high-frequency components up to 150 kHz. Their outputs are connected in parallel and applied simultaneously to both a reference transformer and the device under test. By using this approach, it becomes possible to evaluate the accuracy, phase displacement, and frequency response of voltage transformers under realistic operating conditions, where both fundamental and harmonic components are present.

3.2 Set-up architecture

The generation architecture proposed consists of the parallel connection of a power frequency generator, operating at 50/60 Hz, and a high frequency components generator. Their outputs are summed to provide a composite signal that is applied simultaneously to a reference voltage transformer and the VT under test. The basic block diagram of this setup is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the proposed generation architecture and comparator-based VT characterization method.

This configuration implements a classical characterization method based [6-8] on the comparison of the outputs of a reference VT and a VT under test, using a comparator. The comparator, as well as the reference VT, must have sufficient accuracy over the entire frequency range of interest, from the nominal power frequency up to 150 kHz. By comparing the outputs, it is possible to determine the ratio error and phase displacement of the VT under test both at the fundamental frequency and in the presence of high-frequency components, thereby enabling the assessment of its frequency response and transient performance.

In practice, the Power Frequency Generator (PFG) is implemented by means of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), followed by a low-voltage amplifier and a step-up transformer to achieve the required test voltage levels. The High-Frequency Generator is also realized using an Arbitrary Waveform Generator, cascaded with a low-voltage amplifier, and provides output signals from DC up to 150 kHz. The complete measurement setup is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Setup implementation of the proposed generation setup.

3.3 Setup implementation

The applied voltage signals are provided by a two-channels arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) Keysight 33612A (± 10 V output range, 660 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 64 million of samples per channel of onboard memory). The comparator is realized by a Data Acquisition System (DAQ) PicoScope 5244D MSO (16-bit resolution, 200 MHz bandwidth, ± 20 V maximum input voltage), which acquires the primary and secondary waveforms of the VT under test.

The output of the first channel of the AWG (AWG ch. 1) is connected to a voltage amplifier (± 120 V, ± 50 A, 6 kVA) feeding the VT under test at 50 Hz through a 100 V / 35 kV step up transformer with a power capacity of 5 kVA. Indeed, the transformer T1 and the associated low-frequency amplifier must be able to supply very high power levels because of the blocking elements. Since the blocking capacitors are in the nanofarad range, their impedance at 50 Hz is very low, and consequently a large amount of power is required to maintain the desired test voltage.

The ration of the transformer T1 has been measured. The results show that it exhibits only a very small sensitivity of about 0.3% in its transformation ratio when subjected to different capacitive loads (100 pF, 1 nF, and 2.5 nF) over the voltage range from 5 kV to 35 kV at 50 Hz. The ratio remains essentially stable and only weakly dependent on load conditions, with no need for correction when the load changes. However, the ratio increases from 332 at 5 kV to 340 at 35 kV, which indicates that a correction may be required to account for the voltage dependence if the 50 Hz voltage is to be assigned with high accuracy.

The output of the second AWG (AWG ch. 2) is connected to a power amplifier N4L LPA400 (± 400 V, 50 mA, DC – 1 MHz, selectable gain). The output impedance of the LPA400 amplifier was measured from 50 Hz to 150 kHz and remains essentially constant around 50 Ω . At 50 Hz, the voltage drop across this output impedance is minimal, ensuring that virtually the entire 50 Hz voltage appears across the blocking capacitor C2. Of course the rms current flowing through the LPA400, both the fundamental and harmonics, need to be less than its current capability, a current sensor has been installed in the output of the LPA400 to monitor it. The gain has been also measured from DC to 150 kHz allowing us to generate precisely the desired voltage of harmonics.

The device under test was represented by a RC divider (100 M Ω /100 pF) designed and implemented within a collaboration between LNE and University of Campania “L. Vanvitelli”; it has a scale factor of 50000:1, frequency response remains better than 0.1 % from DC up to 150 kHz, and voltage linearity better than 0.02 % from 5 kV to 35 kV. Such a divider has been placed in the DUT slot of the setup, and it was used to measure the output voltage generated by the whole setup (i.e., the combination of the outputs of the two generators). From this point on, this divider will be addressed as Universal Divider (UD).

Two other dividers have been used to measure 50 Hz and high-frequency voltages respectively, just at the output of the corresponding generators. Divider D1 is a commercial RC divider (300 M Ω /10 pF, ratio 1000:1, accuracy 0.1% at 50 Hz and 1% at 150 kHz). Divider D2 is a commercial RC divider (100 M Ω /3 pF, ratio 1000:1, accuracy 0.1% at 50 Hz and 1% at 150 kHz).

Moreover, a full remote control of the setup has been implemented in LabVIEW environment. The realized software allows to choose generation parameters, to enable and disable the generation, and to monitor overvoltage and overcurrent situations.

3.4 Blocking elements

In this generation architecture, it is necessary to protect each generator from the voltage coming from the other generator. Therefore, two blocking filters have been designed and included. First, a resistor R1 and a capacitor C1 (rated at 50 kV too) are used to protect the step-up transformer from high-frequency current. C1 is a polypropylene film capacitor with voltage coefficient at 50 Hz $< 0.2\%$ and linearity error up to 150 kHz $< 0.1\%$. These elements make up the blocking element n. 1 and create a low-pass effect with a cut-off frequency equal to $f_{(cutoff,1)} \cong 636$ Hz, ensuring that HF components are sufficiently attenuated on the transformer side. Moreover, it should be avoided that an amount of 50 Hz voltage drops across the resistor R1. Therefore, DUT impedance at 50 Hz should be much larger than R1 resistor by a factor of 10 allowing a voltage drop in R1 of only 10 %.

Additionally, a HV capacitor, C2 (rated at 50 kV), is placed on the high-frequency amplifier side. C2 is a ceramic capacitor (N4700 dielectric). Together with the output impedance R2 (50 Ω) of the amplifier itself, it makes up

the blocking element n. 2 and creates a high-pass effect with a cut-off frequency equal to 1.5 MHz, ensuring that the 50 Hz component is almost totally removed. Moreover, as it was previously stated for blocking element n. 1, it should be avoided that an amount of high-frequency voltage drops across capacitor C2. As DUT is made up of resistors and capacitors parallel-connected, for high frequency DUT capacitors dominate. Therefore, for the case at hand, the influence of DUT resistive part is negligible in high frequency, and it can be stated that DUT capacitance should be much smaller than capacitor C2 by a factor of 10 allowing a voltage drop in C2 of only 10 %.

Obviously, if DUT is changed, it is necessary to rescale blocking elements as well taking into account the current and voltage capability of each generator. These current limitations are managed directly on the software. Blocking elements are not influenced by dividers D1 and D2. Divider D1 and D2 have a negligible effect on blocking element since their capacitance only a few pF.

3.5 Generator performance assessment based on waveform analysis

In this system, the generator is fully controlled via dedicated software, which plays a central role in configuring and shaping the signal before it is delivered to the DUT. The software allows the user to precisely define the voltage level, the number and type of harmonic tones, and the phase of each individual frequency component. The generator supports both single-tone and multi-tone operation. All signal parameters are initially defined in the frequency domain. This includes:

- The base frequency (typically 50 Hz),
- The list of harmonics to be included (9 kHz to 150 kHz)
- The amplitude of each harmonic component taking into account the gain of each amplifier
- And the relative phase of each harmonic with respect to the fundamental.

Once the spectral content is defined, the software performs an inverse Fourier synthesis to construct the corresponding time-domain waveform. This waveform is then sent to the amplifiers, which boosts the signal to the required voltage level. This approach ensures that the final signal reaching the DUT is a precisely constructed with an accuracy of about 1 % matching the specifications of the voltage with high fidelity.

The correct operation of the generator in this setup can be verified, in Figure 3, by observing the yellow waveform shown in the upper left section of the diagram. This waveform represents the output voltage at the generator's secondary, and it clearly demonstrates the superposition of a 50 Hz fundamental component with its harmonic content at 150 kHz. The presence of the smooth sinusoidal envelope confirms the dominance of the 50 Hz base frequency, while the higher-frequency oscillations riding on the sinusoid indicate that harmonic components are being accurately generated and added. Importantly, the harmonic structure appears coherent and stable, without signs of distortion. This confirms that the generator is operating correctly, producing a signal that matches the intended spectral content and waveform shape. It also indicates that the amplifier and coupling system are not introducing significant non-linearity or filtering effects that would distort the signal before it reaches the DUT. In summary, the observed waveform validates that the 50 Hz excitation is being produced correctly and, the harmonics are superimposed in a stable and controlled manner, and the generator is delivering a clean, consistent signal suitable for testing the DUT under defined harmonic conditions.

Figure 3. Example of generation of one tone superimposed with the fundamental

The red waveform displayed in the upper right of the Figure 3 corresponds to the output voltage of the high-frequency amplifier, just before the signal is applied to the DUT. This signal is designed to contain primarily harmonic components while the fundamental 50 Hz component is expected to be suppressed by a filtering stage. However, visual inspection reveals a low-frequency modulation pattern superimposed on the high-frequency content. The observed red waveform confirms that the generator delivers the intended high-frequency excitation, with only a minor residual 50 Hz contribution. Since this residual does not lead to amplifier saturation or waveform distortion, it is considered acceptable and non-influential for the measurement scenario.

Figure 4, presents both time-domain and frequency-domain views of a high-voltage signal composed of a 50 Hz fundamental frequency and multiple harmonic tones. In the frequency domain, the central spectrum shows a strong fundamental component at 50 Hz with an amplitude of 96 dBm, confirming that the main excitation signal is correctly generated with very low noise. Superimposed on this are multiple harmonic tones, ranging from 10 kHz to 150 kHz, spaced every 10 kHz. These harmonics display a very consistent amplitude, generally between 43 dBm and 46 dBm, indicating good balance across the harmonic range. This small non-linearity observed in the harmonic amplitudes between 10 kHz and 150 kHz are primarily due to the intrinsic non-linearity of the arbitrary waveform generator used to synthesize the multitoned signal. This non-linearity affect the precise voltage levels delivered at each harmonic frequency and result in slight deviations (in dB) across the spectrum. However, this behaviour is well characterized and could be fully correctable. Through software-based correction, the generator can apply pre-distortion algorithms or frequency-dependent compensation, allowing the user to achieve perfectly flat harmonic amplitudes — either equal across the frequency band (same dB level from 10 kHz to 150 kHz), or following any desired voltage profile.

Figure 4. Generation of multi-tones superimposed with the fundamental

The stability of the harmonic and fundamental components is further supported by the statistic calculations presented in Figure 4:

- The measure P1 is the measurement across the DUT (Figure 2)
- The measure P2 is the measurement across the divider D1 (Figure 2)
- The measure P3 is the measurement across the divider D2 (Figure 2)

The standard deviation values associated with each voltage measurement are extremely low, about 0.035 % at 50 Hz (Measure P1) and about 0.02 % for harmonics (Measure P3). This confirms that both the 50 Hz component and the harmonic tones remain stable over time as required for reproducible and reliable testing. Overall, the generator delivers a clean, well-defined multitoned signal, with both frequency and amplitude content tightly controlled. The combination of low standard deviation, coherent harmonic spacing, and clean time-domain waveform demonstrates that the signal is stable, precise, and suitable for high-voltage harmonic analysis and characterization. We can also see that the measured voltages at points P2 and P1 are 14.229 kV and 14.296 kV respectively, resulting in a very small difference of 67 V rms. This corresponds to a relative deviation of only 0.5%.

3.6 Interaction between both parallel generators

The aim of the conducted tests is to quantify how voltage generation is affected when both generators are active. To this end, test procedure involves three steps:

- Both generators are connected, but only the 50 Hz generator is active;
- Both generators are connected, but only the high-frequency generator is active;
- Both generators are connected and active.

In the following, the first two tests are indicated using the subscript “S”, whereas the third one is addressed by the subscript “FHF”. The amplitude of the fundamental component is chosen equal to 12 kV. The frequency of the high-frequency tone varies from 10 kHz to 150 kHz, while its amplitude is chosen as equal to 1 % of fundamental tone.

The ratio error $\varepsilon(f)$ has been calculated comparing the amplitudes generated during the single-tone generation to the ones generated in the FHF test. Mathematically, the ratio error $\varepsilon(f)$ is defined as in (1):

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{V_{FHF}(f) - V_S(f)}{V_S(f)} \quad (1)$$

where:

- $V_{FHF}(f)$ is the measured voltage at frequency f under the FHF test;
- $V_S(f)$ is the measured voltage at frequency f under the S test.

As the only difference between the single-tone generation S test and the FHF test is the presence of both generators, the index $\varepsilon(f)$ estimates their mutual influence. In the following, experimental results are provided and discussed. Figure 5 provides the values of the errors $\varepsilon(f)$ associated to the generated high-frequency tones.

Figure 5. Impact of the simultaneous presence of both generators on the generated high-frequency tone vs. frequency

With regards to Figure 5, it can be observed that the mutual influence of the two generators is relatively low up to 50 kHz, because the error $\varepsilon(f)$ is less than 2 %. Up to 100 kHz, the error is below 3 %, whereas at 150 kHz it increases to 6 %. As the error curve has a negative polarity for all the frequencies, it means that, during FHF tests, HF tone amplitudes decrease due to the simultaneous presence of the other generator, with respect to S test. This behavior can be explained by the voltage dependence of capacitor C2, which uses an N4700 dielectric known for its poor stability under high voltage at 50 Hz. When the 50 Hz component is applied, the dielectric’s properties vary with voltage, leading to a non-linear response. This voltage dependence affects the behavior of the blocking element and can introduce unwanted variations in the signal. For applications involving high 50 Hz voltage, a capacitor made with a polypropylene dielectric would be more suitable, as it offers better linearity and lower voltage dependence.

With respect to the error at 50 Hz (Figure 6), it can be observed that it is much lower, and it is lower than ± 0.1 %. Moreover, the frequency of the high-frequency tone does not significantly influence the error at 50 Hz.

Figure 6. Impact of the simultaneous presence of both generators on the generated 50 Hz tone vs. frequency

Therefore, it can be concluded that the biggest influence is from the 50 Hz generator to the high-frequency one, whereas the 50 Hz generation is little affected by the mutual presence of both generators.

3.7 Influence of the blocking elements

This section provides some results to evaluate the effect of the blocking elements.

The residual high-frequency voltage measured by D1 has been compared to the full voltage measured by UD. Mathematically, it was calculated as in (2):

$$res_{HF}(f) = \frac{V_{D1}(f)}{V_{UD}(f)} \quad (2)$$

Figure 7 provides the values of $res_{HF}(f)$ vs. the frequency of the generated high-frequency tone. It can be observed that the residual $res_{HF}(f)$ decreases with frequency, because the higher the frequency, the farther you are from cutoff frequency.

On the other side, the residual 50 Hz voltage $res_{(50 \text{ Hz})}$ measured by D2 has been compared to the full voltage measured by UD. Mathematically, it was calculated as in (3):

$$res_{50 \text{ Hz}} = \frac{V_{D2}(50 \text{ Hz})}{V_{UD}(50 \text{ Hz})} \quad (3)$$

Figure 8 provides the values of $res_{(50 \text{ Hz})}(f)$ vs. the frequency of the generated high-frequency tone. The cut-off frequency of the blocking element n. 2 is high enough to avoid significant 50 Hz voltage to be present at the input of the high-frequency amplifier. It can be observed that the residual 50 Hz voltage which falls across the high-frequency generator output is less than 0.002 % of the generated 50 Hz voltage. That ensures safety for the high-frequency amplifier and avoids that the 50 Hz current coming from the 50 Hz side and flowing into high-frequency amplifier is too high.

Figure 7. Percentage of high-frequency voltage measured by D1 compared to full high-frequency voltage measured by UD vs. frequency

Figure 8. Percentage of 50 Hz voltage measured by D2 compared to full 50 Hz voltage measured by UD vs. frequency

3.8 Conclusion

This chapter presents a generation system for the characterization of voltage transformers, for Medium Voltage grids, in the frequency range from power frequency (50/60 Hz) and for harmonics in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The proposed generation system is based on the separate generation of the 50 Hz fundamental tone and the high-frequency components. The two generators are grounded and parallel-connected to obtain the composed voltage waveform. Two blocking elements have been added to the setup to prevent 50 Hz current from flowing into the high-frequency generator, and vice versa. The generator configuration presented in this system offers a flexible and practical solution for injecting combined 50 Hz and high-frequency signals into various types of DUT such as voltage transformers. Its modular design makes it easy to install in different environments, including industrial test benches or laboratory setups.

The use of adjustable blocking elements allows the system to be adapted to a wide range of DUTs with varying electrical characteristics. By tuning the values of the blocking element the system can optimize the coupling between low-frequency and high-frequency sources while maintaining electrical isolation and protecting the amplifiers. The required signal levels can be achieved using different types of amplifiers, depending on the application. Furthermore, the entire system can be integrated with a remote control interface, which facilitates automated test procedures. This feature is especially valuable for routine testing in industrial environments, enabling operators to perform tests more safely, efficiently, and with repeatable results.

This generator architecture is also highly scalable and adaptable. It can be extended to operate at frequencies up to 500 kHz, simply by selecting appropriate high-frequency amplifiers and adapting the blocking elements accordingly. In addition to sinusoidal excitations, the system can also be used to superimpose other types of signals, such as impulses, transients, or damped oscillatory waveforms, making it suitable for a wide range of test applications.

4 Series connected generators for AC Voltage at UniCampania

4.1 Introduction

This section introduces a novel generation and measurement setup developed at the University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli” for the frequency characterization of voltage transformers. The system is based on the independent generation of the fundamental power-frequency component, obtained through an Arbitrary Waveform Generator, a low-frequency amplifier, and a step-up transformer, and of the high-frequency components, produced by a second generator and a high-frequency amplifier. By connecting these sources in series, the setup enables the creation of distorted test waveforms composed of a rated 50 Hz voltage with superimposed harmonic tones in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. Dedicated reference devices and a high-resolution acquisition system ensure accurate measurement of both the power-frequency and harmonic components. This flexible configuration provides a practical solution for reproducing realistic distorted signals at medium-voltage levels, supporting advanced studies on the accuracy and frequency response of voltage transformers.

4.2 Design and development

In Figure 9a, the general block scheme of the proposed novel setup is presented, whereas a picture is shown in Figure 9b. The setup has been realized at University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli” and used in a temperature-controlled room. The most commonly used test waveforms for the VT frequency characterization are composed of fundamental tone at the rated frequency and amplitude and one or more superimposed tones at different frequencies and with reduced amplitudes. The proposed solution involves the independent generation of the fundamental tone and of the high frequency components to produce the desired distorted test waveform.

According to a commonly used practice in calibration laboratories (but also at NMI level), the generation of fundamental frequency components up to hundreds of kilovolt can be obtained by means of Step-Up voltage Transformers (SUT). Similarly, the proposed architecture generates the fundamental component using an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG1), a low-voltage and Low-Frequency Amplifier (LFA), and a SUT. Due to its intrinsic galvanic insulation, this method allows for the generation of a voltage waveform with respect to a desired reference potential. It is important to underline that the desired reference potential should not necessarily be the earth potential or the reference potential of the rest of the circuit, thanks to the galvanic insulation of the SUT. Therefore, the secondary winding of the SUT can be easily series connected with another generation system as well depicted in Figure 9c.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 9. Basic block scheme (a), picture (b) and circuit diagram (c) of the proposed generation and measurement setup arranged at University of Campania

Considering that the frequency components have an amplitude lower than fundamental components, up to 3%, they can be generated using AWG2 coupled with a high-frequency amplifier (HFA). Thus, the distorted test waveforms can be obtained by simply using the SUT and HFA connected in series to superimpose the frequency components in the range [9, 150] kHz to the MV component at 50 Hz.

As regards the measurement section, two different reference transducers are used, one (LFRD, Low Frequency Reference Device, calibrated at INRIM) for the measurement of the power frequency component at MV level and the other (HFRD, High Frequency Reference Device) for the measurement of the high frequency components, characterised by amplitudes in the range up to hundreds of volt. It is worth noting that one of the main goals of the ADMIT project is the design, the realization and the characterization of reference sensors operating in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz and capable to work at MV amplitude levels.

As regard the acquisition section, the comparator is realized by using a Data Acquisition (DAQ) module that acquires the outputs of the device under test, of LFRD and of HFRD. Gain and offset of the adopted DAQ have been determined at INRIM. The DAQ module is installed in a PXI chassis along with the AWGs; the 10 MHz PXI clock is used as a reference clock for the AWGs Phase Locked Loop (PLL) circuitry. The time base of AWG1 provides also the sampling clock for the digitizer; this allows obtaining coherent sampling, thus avoiding spectral leakage.

Moreover, in Figure 9c, the impedances Z_1 , Z_2 and Z_3 (green colour) are the input impedance of DAQ channels. Moreover, if the DUT output voltage is too high to directly be acquired by the DAQ (as in the case of inductive VTs), a Low Voltage Divider (LVD) is used (see Figure 9a). This divider can be characterized by NMIs at voltage levels in the range of hundreds of volt up to 150 kHz.

The main specifications of the various devices used to implement the described setup are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Main specifications of the setup components

NAME	MAIN FEATURES
AWGS	National Instruments (NI) PCI eXtension for Instrumentation (PXI) 5422, 16-bit, variable output gain, ± 12 V output range, 200 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 256 MB of onboard memory.
LFA	Voltage amplifier, ± 75 V, ± 20 A, 1 kW, DC – 100 kHz
SUT	Step-Up Voltage Transformers, 100 V / 24 kV
HFA	Voltage amplifier, ± 150 V, 200 VA, DC – 500 kHz.
DAQ	Data acquisition module NI PXIe-6124, ± 10 V, 16 bit, maximum sampling rate of 4 MHz, input resistance >100 G Ω with parallel 10 pF.
LFRD	Commercial resistive-capacitive divider, 10 / 10 kV/V, uncertainty of 0.01% and 100 μ rad @ 50 Hz (level of confidence 95 %)
LVD	Commercial resistive divider, 18.5 V/V, uncertainty of 0.01% and 100 μ rad @ 50 Hz (level of confidence 95 %)

The series connection of the two generators presents some issues that must be addressed in order to make this architecture suitable for the scope at hand.

First of all, according to the equivalent circuit of a voltage, the equivalent impedance $\dot{Z}_s(f)$ of the secondary winding, in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz, is mainly inductive and increases with frequency. Therefore, in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz the equivalent circuit (shown in Figure 10) of the measurement setup is constituted by the HFA and its load, that is the series connection of $\dot{Z}_s(f)$ and $\dot{Z}_m(f)$, that, in turns, is the equivalent impedance resulting from the parallel of the input impedances of DUT, LFRD and HFRD.

Figure 11. Equivalent circuit of the setup at the primary side of SUT

Looking at the Figure 10, it can be seen that the output voltage of HFA is divided among $\dot{Z}_s(f)$ and $\dot{Z}_m(f)$. The voltage drop across $\dot{Z}_s(f)$, that is undesired, increases with frequency, making thus the portion of voltage across $\dot{Z}_m(f)$ smaller and smaller. To avoid this issue, it is possible to add a capacitor C_s in parallel to the secondary winding of SUT in order to drastically reduce the voltage drop across $\dot{Z}_s(f)$.

However, the insertion of C_s at the SUT output increases the load of LFA. In fact, the equivalent impedance $\dot{Z}_s(f)$ (including now C_s), transferred at the primary side of SUT, must be sufficiently high, at 50 Hz, to stay within the current limit of LFA (LFA generates voltage and current at 50 Hz). Since the rated transformation ratio of SUT is $k = \frac{N_p}{N_s}$, where N_p (N_s) is the number of turns at primary (secondary) winding, the load impedance of LFA is $\dot{Z}_p(50) = k^2 \dot{Z}_s(50)$. In the case of SUT, N_s is higher than N_p and then k is lower than 1. Therefore, the magnitude Z_p of \dot{Z}_p is lower than Z_s . To calculate the maximum value of C_s , the current of primary winding

of SUT must be considered. For sake of clarity, Figure 11 shows the circuit for the calculation of $C_{s,max}$. The current I_1 is the maximum LFA output current, which divides in I_2 and I_z , which are, respectively, the current that flows in the primary winding of SUT and the current that flows in Z_p . I_2 depends on the load of the SUT. However, generally, the load impedance of SUT is high; therefore, the I_2 can be assumed to be the magnetizing current of SUT. Therefore, the maximum value of C_s is calculated by the following equation:

$$C_{s,max} = \frac{I_z}{2\pi f_1 V_1} \quad (4)$$

where V_1 and f_1 are, respectively, the maximum magnitude of the fundamental voltage phasor and its frequency and I_z is the difference between I_1 and I_2 . For the case at hand, $C_{s,max}$ is equal to 50 nF.

As regards the current limit of HFA, the magnitude of the equivalent series impedance of $Z_s(f)$ and $Z_m(f)$ must be sufficiently high to stay within the current limitation of HFA in the frequency range [9, 150] kHz. This condition generally holds, since the input impedance of the VTs designed for MV applications is generally high. However, it is worth noting that a check against the limitations of the HFA generator must be done before the execution of the tests.

4.3 Conclusion

In summary, the proposed setup provides a flexible and accurate way to generate distorted test waveforms by combining a fundamental 50 Hz component with controlled high-frequency tones. Its modular design, based on independent low- and high-frequency sources, ensures reliable medium-voltage testing and supports detailed characterization of voltage transformers across a wide frequency range.

5 Using a step up transformer for AC Voltage at INRIM

5.1 Introduction

The proposed generation architecture is simpler and more cost-effective compared to those presented in previous sections as it is tailored for industrial laboratories with standard equipment like Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG), wideband LV power amplifier, and commercial step-up transformer (SUT). Its key advantages are the use of a single voltage source for the generation of distorted waveforms with both power frequency and HF content and no need for a high-voltage capacitor. However, frequency-dependent performance, especially of the SUT, necessitates a compensation technique to ensure the correct high-frequency generation.

5.2 General voltage generator architecture and test procedure

Figure 12 shows the proposed voltage generation architecture, it includes an AWG, a wideband LV power amplifier and a SUT.

The objective is to supply the VT/LPVT under test and the reference device with MV test waveforms representative of the realistic ones. The considered actual waveforms consist of a multitone voltage signal composed by a fundamental component at the rated voltage V_0 and frequency f_0 and a number of superimposed tones, ranging from 1 up to a generic number N . Each of these tones has reduced amplitude $V_{HF,k}$ and higher frequency $f_{HF,k}$, as described in Equation 5:

$$v_G(t) = \sqrt{2}V_0 \sin(2\pi f_0 t) + \sqrt{2} \sum_{k=1}^N V_{HF,k} \sin(2\pi f_{HF,k} t) \quad (5)$$

Contrarily from the architectures presented in Section 2 and Section 3, where two different voltage generation sources have been used to generate the component at f_0 and those at f_{HF} , here the distorted waveform $v_G(t)$ is produced using a single-generation setup. The proposed architecture offers a significant cost advantage, as it requires only a single wideband amplifier and does not include a high-voltage capacitor.

However, a critical drawback of the generation architecture in Figure 12 is that the resulting distorted MV signal does not represent an amplified version of the target waveform.

Figure 12. General scheme of the proposed setup for VT characterization up to 150 kHz

This discrepancy mainly arises because SUTs are known to exhibit a non-flat frequency response over a wide frequency range since they experience filtering effects, frequency resonance [9], [10] and non-linearity phenomena [11]. However, experiments under laboratory controlled temperature has evidenced that the non-linearity issue is significant only up to 1 kHz [11], so considering the ADMIT [9-150] kHz target range, the generation system in Figure 12 can be considered composed of linear elements. Starting from this assumption, the non-ideal frequency behavior problem can be solved by first measuring the frequency response functions of the three elements of the generation section. Then, these measurement data can be used to produce a dataset of test waveforms according to equation (6), designed to compensate for distortions introduced by the elements of the generation system.

Table 2. Step up VT specifications

Rated input voltage (kV)	Turns ratio	Accuracy Class	Rated Burden (VA)
100/ $\sqrt{3}$	200	0.5	30

As the acquisition system, a NI 9223 board has been used (± 10 V, 16 bit, 1 MHz sampling rate). When used in comparator mode, that is using two acquisition channels, the frequency response in the range [10, 150] kHz is flat within ± 70 μ V/V

The signal acquisition and the voltage generation were managed by LabVIEW program, whereas the post processing was performed in MATLAB environment.

Figure 14. General scheme of the proposed setup for VT characterization up to 150 kHz

5.4 Performance of the proposed setup in HF tone generation

The first experimental activity aims to assess the performance of the developed generation system and demonstrate its ability to produce distorted waveforms with spectral content up to 150 kHz. The tests are carried out under controlled laboratory temperature conditions ($23\text{ C} \pm 1\text{ C}$). The evaluation procedure consists of two main steps:

1. identifying the compensation functions for the three elements of the generation chain, and
2. verifying the system's performance after applying the compensation.

5.4.1 Identification of the compensation functions

Starting with the identification step, the frequency functions $\bar{G}_{AWG}(f)$, $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$ and $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ are measured by performing a sinusoidal frequency sweep (SFS) in the range [10, 150] kHz.

More in detail, for the AWG, its frequency response is measured by programming it to generate a virtually pure sinewave at 1 V and varying the frequency within the range of 10 kHz to 150 kHz. The produced voltages are measured and the module of $\bar{G}_{AWG}(f)$ is computed as the ratio between the output voltage of the AWG and the expected reference voltage of 1 V.

For the measurement of the power amplifier compensation function $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$, it is set to have a rated amplification gain of 100 V/V; it is supplied with a SFS at 70 mV using the Fluke 5730 A calibrator. The $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$ function is then computed using the input and output voltages acquired by the NI 9223 board. The approach used for the power amplifier characterization is also applied to the identification of the SUT compensation function. It involves supplying the SUT with a SFS at rated voltage ($100/\sqrt{3}$ V) and measuring both the input and output voltages. In this case, RCVD_B is connected to the SUT to account for the burden effect while simultaneously scaling down the SUT output voltage to ensure compatibility with the input range of the acquisition system. The characterization results for SUT are presented in Figure 15 in terms of $\bar{G}_{AMP}(f)$

module. As can be observed, several resonances occur over the investigated frequency range. The SUT gain module is always lower than the rated value (200 V/V) and it varies from a maximum of 42.6 V/V at 14.85 kHz to a minimum of 0.24 V/V at 104 kHz.

Figure 15. General scheme of the proposed setup for VT characterization up to 150 kHz

5.4.2 Verification of the generation system performance

For the evaluation of the generation system performance, an appropriately distorted test waveform is digitally synthesized. The chosen test signal consists of a fundamental tone with one superimposed HF component, referred to as the FHF1 test. The fundamental tone is set to 3 kV at 50 Hz, while the amplitude of the HF component is adjusted to be 1 % of the fundamental tone within the range of 10 kHz - 150 kHz. The adjustment is made according to Equation (6) by considering the frequency gains measured during the identification step described in Section 4.3.1. The distorted MV waveforms are then generated, and a 5-second acquisition is performed. Post-processing analysis involves applying a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) over 10 cycles of the fundamental tone.

To quantify the performance of the generation setup, the index in Equation 7 is used:

$$\varepsilon(f) = 1 - \frac{|\overline{SF_{RCVD_B}}(f) \cdot \overline{V_{HF,meas}}(f)|}{|\overline{V_{HF,desired}}(f)|} \quad (7)$$

where $\overline{SF_{RCVD_B}}(f)$ is the SF frequency function of the reference RCVD_B; $\overline{V_{HF,meas}}(f)$ and $\overline{V_{HF,desired}}(f)$ are the root mean square (rms) values of the measured and desired HF components, respectively.

The index defined in (7) quantifies the deviation between the generated HF voltage and the target value, providing an appropriate metric to assess the error introduced by the proposed generation system.

For the setup described in Section 4.2, results in terms of $\varepsilon(f)$ are provided in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Errors $\varepsilon(f)$ associated with HF tones measured when the generation system is used to generate a FHF1 voltages.

As can be observed, over the entire investigated frequency range the error goes from 0.06 % to 0.56 %. In general, it never exceeds 1 % which can be considered a satisfactory threshold.

5.5 Impact of influence quantities on the SUT

This section presents the analysis and experimental activity conducted to assess the impact of external factors on the performance of the proposed generation approach.

In particular, it is investigate on the effect of temperature variation and burden condition on the $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ used to design the compensation function.

5.5.1 Temperature

To assess the impact of temperature variation on the SUT frequency gain, the SUT is placed inside a climatic chamber (100x100x120 cm³, from -80 °C to +180 °C) whereas the rest of the generation and measurement system is kept at constant ambient temperature.

Tests are performed at three different temperatures: 20 °C, 25 °C and 30 °C. The tested SUT has a thermal class of -5/40; however, its performances are investigated in a narrower temperature range, reflecting the possible realistic fluctuations occurring throughout the year in a test laboratory without temperature control.

The SUT is supplied with a sinusoidal waveform at rated voltage and with frequency from 10 kHz and 150 kHz. The output voltage is acquired with the RCVD_B connected to the SUT.

To quantify how the variability of $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ due to the temperature impacts on the performance of the proposed system a specific analysis is performed. First, $\bar{V}_{SYNT}(f)$ is synthesized using the $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ compensation function measured at the reference temperature of 25 °C. The system is then cooled/warm up, reaching the steady-state temperatures of 20 °C/30 °C. At this stage, the verification step, as described in Section 4.3.2, is carried out and the measured indices $\varepsilon(f)$ are summarized in Table 3.

As first comment, it can be observed that the results for the two cases differ in sign indicating that at 20 °C, the module of $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ is higher than the one measured at 25 °C, whereas at 30 °C, it is lower than at 25 °C. The errors due to thermal variations are significant, with the most critical case observed at 30 °C, where the error $\varepsilon(f)$ is one order of magnitude higher than the error observed in the analysis conducted at a constant temperature (Figure 16). These results suggest that, to keep low the uncertainty associated with HF tones generated by the proposed system, it is necessary to monitor the temperature during the test session. If significant temperature variations occur between the identification step and the testing phase on the VT under test, the appropriate gain curves of the SUT should be measured and used to synthesize $\bar{V}_{SYNT}(f)$.

Table 3. Impact of SUT operating temperature on $\varepsilon(f)$

Temperature (°C)	Frequency (kHz)			
	10	50	80	100
20	-3.0 %	-2.3 %	-2.4 %	-2.2 %
30	6.8 %	7.8 %	7.2 %	7.3 %

5.5.2 Burden

To evaluate how burden affects the frequency gain of the SUT, SFS tests with both RCVD_A and RCVD_B used as load are performed. From the burden point of view and considering the investigated range, the most significant difference between the two devices is the input capacitance C_{in} . For RCVD_A the input capacitance is equal to 780 pF whereas for RCVD_B is two orders of magnitude lower, that is 8 pF.

Table 4 provides the SUT module gains measured when it is used to supply the two different RCVDs.

The module of $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ measured under the two different burdens conditions show a remarkable difference: with RCVD_A, the module of the $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ is approximately five times lower than with RCVD_B over the entire investigated frequency range. Therefore, as expected, the identification step should be performed with the device under test (DUT) and the reference VT already connected to the circuit in order to account for burden effect.

Table 4: Impact of burden on the module of $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$

Frequency (kHz)	10	50	80
$ \bar{G}_{SUT}(f) $ with RCVD _A (V/V)	0.72	0.21	0.08
$ \bar{G}_{SUT}(f) $ with RCVD _B (V/V)	3.52	1.27	0.44
Frequency (kHz)	100	130	150
$ \bar{G}_{SUT}(f) $ with RCVD _A (V/V)	0.05	0.05	0.09
$ \bar{G}_{SUT}(f) $ with RCVD _B (V/V)	0.29	0.30	0.47

5.6 Conclusions

From the analysis of the results shown in previous sections, some general considerations are here provided. The experimental activity performed on the setup shown in Figure 12, indicates that, after the appropriate compensation function is measured and implemented, the generation system produces frequency tones with associated errors lower than 0.56 % over the frequency range going from 10 kHz to 150 kHz. However, this level of performance can be significantly influenced by variations in external factors, specifically temperature and burden conditions. In particular, it was found that temperature strongly impacts on the performance of the generation system. For instance, in case of temperature variation of the SUT from 25 °C to 30 °C, the error associated with the HF tone can increase of one order of magnitude, going from a maximum of 0.56 % to ~8 %.

Regarding the burden effect on the system, it was evidenced that varying burden lead to significant variations of the module of $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ of some order of magnitude.

The analysis on the effects of temperature and burden revealed that the test procedure for using the proposed generation setup should include two important steps:

- the measurement of the generation system frequency gains with the circuit set up in the final test configuration to accurately account for the real burden;
- the tracking of temperature during long-duration tests in uncontrolled environments to evaluate if it is necessary to repeat the identification step to measure the proper $\bar{G}_{SUT}(f)$ function.

6 Series connected Generators for DC Voltage at FFII

6.1 Introduction

This section presents the development of a generation system capable of superimposing high-frequency AC components onto a high-voltage DC signal. The concept relies on connecting a regulated HVDC source in series with a high-frequency voltage transformer, driven by an arbitrary waveform generator and a broadband amplifier. This configuration enables the production of distorted test waveforms, where a stable DC level is combined with controlled supraharmmonic tones in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz. The setup was conceived to evaluate the interaction between DC and AC sources, verify insulation strategies, and provide a flexible tool for testing instrument transformers under combined DC and supraharmmonic conditions.

6.2 Preliminary tests of two series generators arranged at FFII

The series-generator, Figure 17, setup consisted of two main subsystems connected in series: (1) a high-voltage DC source, and (2) a high-frequency AC source with a step-up transformer. The conceptual schematic is illustrated in the following scheme for clarity:

Figure 17. Conceptual schematic of the preliminary two series generator.

1. High-Voltage DC Generator: A regulated HV DC supply capable of up to 50 kV output was used to generate the DC component. A HV filter/inductor was placed in series with the DC output to allow steady DC current flow while blocking AC (thus preventing the HF harmonics from feeding back into the DC supply). The DC source was ramped to the desired voltage during tests.
2. High-Frequency AC Source: To generate the supraharmmonic components, a programmable arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) produced sinusoidal signals in the target frequency range (9 kHz up to 150 kHz for these tests). The AWG output was amplified by a broadband power amplifier (rated approximately 150–200 W over the frequency range of interest). The amplifier could output up to ~100–150 VAC into a load and was configured with no DC offset (pure AC output mode).
3. High-Frequency Voltage Transformer (HFVT): A step-up transformer was used to couple the amplifier's low-voltage AC output into the high-voltage circuit. The HFVT had a ferrite core and was designed to have a high turns ratio (for example, an initial prototype used ~10 primary turns to 25 secondary turns) to increase the voltage, with the secondary winding insulated for several tens of kV. The HFVT's secondary was connected in series with the HVDC circuit. Several HFVT configurations were tested over the course of Task A2.1.3 (modifying the turns ratio and core sizes) to improve the performance (as discussed later in results). To ensure proper insulation in the high-voltage section, the final design of the HFVT consisted of a series arrangement of two transformers:

- a. The first transformer, with a 5:5 ratio, featured high insulation in both wirings to properly insulate the AWG from the high voltage.
- b. The second transformer, with a 5:5 ratio, intended to step up the voltage from the power amplifier to the HVDC circuit. Its LV wiring had 5 turns of HV insulated cable, while its HV wiring had 50 turns of copper wire.

The reason behind this transformer configuration was primarily to ensure sufficient insulation between the high-voltage (HV) and low-voltage (LV) windings. Since the system needed to withstand up to 50 kV DC, it was essential that one winding be constructed using HV cable. However, placing the HV cable on the high-voltage side would have significantly degraded the transformer's frequency response, due to the considerable distance between the winding and the core in every turn. Therefore, the HV cable was implemented on the low voltage winding instead, preserving a better frequency response while still providing the required insulation. To further enhance dielectric isolation, an additional HV transformer was connected in series with the primary transformer, resulting in a cascaded arrangement that increased overall safety and voltage-withstand capability. Figure 18 shows an image of this arrangement.

Figure 18. Preliminary High Frequency Voltage Transformer.

4. Load and Measurement: The output of the combined system (the junction of the HV DC source, HFVT secondary, and coupling capacitor) was applied to a load representative of an instrument transformer's impedance. This was largely capacitive, dominated by the input capacitance of the measuring equipment itself – specifically, a high-voltage divider used to measure the output waveform had approximately 1 nF capacitance. Thus ~1 nF served as the test load in these preliminary verifications. The HV divider (1000:1 ratio) was connected to an oscilloscope to record both the DC level and the AC waveform simultaneously. The series combination of the HV supply, HFVT, and load completed the circuit, with the ground reference at the low side of the HV divider and the return of the HV supply.

6.3 Test results

6.3.1 AC-only tests

The objective of these tests was to characterize the output of the high frequency voltage transformer without load. Sinusoidal AC of several frequencies (typically 15, 25, 50, 100, 150 kHz and some intermediate points) was applied via the amplifier and HFVT. At each frequency, the AC amplitude was incrementally increased until one of two limits was reached: either the HFVT began to saturate (detected by a deviation of the output waveform from a sinusoidal shape or a plateauing of output despite increasing drive) or the amplifier's current/voltage limit was hit (preventing further increase). This established the maximum AC voltage the system could generate at that frequency into the given load. The waveform shapes and values were recorded. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a picture of this setup.

The achievable output was limited at low frequencies by the HFVT’s core saturation and improved at higher frequencies as the core’s inductive reactance increased. At approximately 15 kHz, the maximum AC voltage reached was on the order of 100 V_{RMS} before the waveform started to show distortion (signifying the onset of core saturation in the small transformer). By 40–50 kHz, the system could produce about 500 V_{RMS} without issues. In the upper part of the range, around 100 kHz and above, the output approached 800 V_{RMS} .

The trend shows that the AC voltage output rose with frequency. At higher frequency, less time per half-cycle means the core could handle a higher voltage before saturating. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the results obtained in this test for the final HFVT by using only the 5:50 transformer.

Figure 19. AC only test setup.

Figure 20. Maximum harmonic voltage generation capability of the preliminary HFVT

Figure 22. Maximum harmonic voltage generation capability of the preliminary generator.

6.4 Final DC Generation System

In Task A2.1.5, the insights from the preliminary tests were applied to build the full-capability DC + HF generation system. The design was scaled up to 50 kV and multi-kilowatt levels, with additional measures for stability and safety. The conceptual circuit scheme was revised so that the HFVT is no longer included in the high-voltage section. Instead, high-frequency signals can be injected through the ground path, placing the HFVT and related components at ground potential. This change dramatically simplifies insulation requirements and enhances safety, as the transformer is no longer exposed to the full high voltage.

Figure 23. Conceptual schematic of the final DC generation system.

The system architecture included the following components and design choices:

- **High-Voltage DC Supply:** The same HVDC source that was used during the preliminary tests. A regulated HV DC supply capable of up to ~50 kV output was used to generate the DC component. A HV filter/inductor was placed in series with the DC output to allow steady DC current flow while blocking AC (thus preventing the HF harmonics from feeding back into the DC supply). The DC source was ramped to the desired voltage during tests.

- **Wideband AC Power Amplifier:** For the AC injection, a significantly more powerful amplifier was chosen compared to Task A2.1.3. A 5 kVA wideband power amplifier (with frequency range from DC up to ~250 kHz) was procured and integrated. This amplifier could deliver up to ± 150 V and up to tens of amperes of current. The amplifier was driven by an AWG to produce steady-state sinusoids for each test. The amplifier's high power allowed driving the large capacitive loads at high frequency without severe voltage drop.
- **High-Frequency Injection Transformer:** The HFVT was a refined version of the concept used in Task A2.1.3. Based on the earlier findings, the HFVT was constructed with a substantially larger ferrite core, roughly four times the core volume of the initial prototype. This increase in core size raised the saturation flux threshold, enabling the transformer to handle the combined DC plus AC over the full frequency range without saturating. The transformer's turns ratio and winding were designed to output 1 kV_{RMS} of AC at the secondary when applying 100 V_{RMS}, resulting in a turns ratio of 1:10. Previously, the HFVT was part of the high-voltage node and required insulation capable of withstanding the full 50 kV, which complicated the design and reduced the frequency response capability. With the new architecture, however, the high-frequency injection point was moved to ground, allowing the HFVT and associated components to operate at ground potential. Thanks to this redesign, it is no longer necessary to provide the transformer with the extreme insulation previously required, which greatly simplifies construction and allows for optimized frequency performance, achieving much better results in the harmonic injection.
- **Load and Measurement:** The output was connected to a combined load of approximately 3.5 nF, which was intentionally chosen as a worst-case capacitive load. This 3.5 nF represented the parallel combination of the HV divider used for measurement (~1 nF) and an additional capacitive load (~2.5 nF) to simulate an instrument transformer's input capacitance.

6.5 Test results

Testing began with incremental validation: for example, injecting a moderate AC voltage (a few hundred volts) at incremental frequencies while the DC was set at a lower value (10–20 kV). Once the AC injection path was verified to be working correctly and no abnormal behavior was observed, the DC was increased stepwise to the full 50 kV.

The main test campaign involved sweeping through frequencies between 9 kHz and 150 kHz, covering the standard supraharmmonic range, and, at each frequency, increasing the AC amplitude until either the target voltage, ~1 kV_{RMS} at the output, was reached or the amplifier approached its current/voltage limit. Throughout these tests, the waveform shape was examined to ensure it remained sinusoidal to check that the HFVT was not saturating or distorting the signal. The presence of the 50 kV DC was continuously checked and remained stable, indicating the HF coupling did not disturb the DC supply. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows an image of the final DC generation system.

Figure 24. Final test setup of the preliminary tests of two series generator.

1. AWG + HF Amplifier: Output $\sim 0\text{--}150\text{ V}_{AC}$, $0\text{--}250\text{ kHz}$, max $\sim 5000\text{ W}$ (current-limited).
2. HF Voltage Transformer: Final version with a 1:10 ratio.
3. HV Divider (Load): 1000:1 divider, $\sim 1\text{ nF}$ capacitance.
4. HV capacitor in parallel with the HVDC supply.
5. HV DC Supply: $\sim 0\text{--}50\text{ kV}$ adjustable.

With the upgraded design in Task A2.1.5, the HV generation system's performance was improved, meeting the project's requirements across the spectrum. Testing at up to $\sim 50\text{ kV}$ DC and with the 3.5 nF load yielded the following key results:

The final DC generation system achieved approximately 1.0 kV_{RMS} of AC output superimposed on 50 kV DC throughout a broad middle band of frequencies. From about 9 kHz up to $\sim 75\text{ kHz}$, the system could drive the 3.5 nF load to the full target amplitude of $\sim 1000\text{ V}_{RMS}$ without reaching the amplifier's limit or the transformer's saturation. Above 75 kHz , as frequency increases, the load's capacitive reactance decreases, and the current demand rises significantly. For this reason, as a precaution and to avoid excessive power draw from the amplifier, the maximum AC output voltage was intentionally limited to 500 V_{RMS} beyond this frequency range. Achieving higher voltages—potentially up to 1000 V_{RMS} —even at higher frequencies is theoretically possible. However, this would require modifying the resistive loading elements in the amplifier, as the current load resistors were not designed for greater dissipation and resulted in considerable heating at higher output levels.

These values represent a worst-case scenario with a heavy capacitive load. Notably, if the load were of a lower capacitance value, e.g. 1 nF (more typical of high voltage capacitive dividers) instead of 3.5 nF , the system would be capable of supplying 1 kV_{RMS} even at 150 kHz – indicating that the limiting factor at high frequency is the load current demand rather than the source voltage capability. In all cases, the presence of the full 50 kV DC did not affect the AC output; the HFVT was designed to handle the combined flux and did so without any sign of distress.

Error! Reference source not found. shows the maximum harmonic voltage generation capability of the DC voltage generation system. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows an example of the combined waveforms of HVDC and supraharmonics recorded by the oscilloscope.

Figure 25. Maximum harmonic voltage generation capability of the DC voltage generation system.

Figure 26. Example of a HVDC + supraharmonics recording.

6.6 Conclusion

The series-connected generator approach has proven effective in generating combined DC and high-frequency voltages up to 50 kV DC with superimposed AC tones in the supraharmonic range. Preliminary tests confirmed that the DC component does not significantly affect the AC injection, while the improved design with a larger HF transformer and ground-referenced injection ensures better safety, insulation, and frequency performance. The final system demonstrated the capability to deliver up to 1 kVRMS of harmonic voltage across capacitive loads while maintaining waveform stability and linearity. This solution provides a robust and scalable platform for characterizing devices under DC bias conditions with added supraharmonics.

7 Transient voltage generator at FFII

7.1 Introduction

This section presents the design and characterization of a Transient Voltage Generator developed to reproduce damped sinusoidal waveforms in the frequency range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz with peak amplitudes up to 3 kV. The generator is intended to emulate realistic high-frequency overvoltages occurring in medium-voltage networks, thereby enabling the testing of instrument transformers under conditions that go beyond the 50/60 Hz fundamental. The system is based on a resonant RLC discharge circuit, where a capacitor is charged to a defined voltage and then discharged through an inductive network via a fast semiconductor switch. By selecting appropriate capacitor and inductor values, the oscillation frequency can be tuned to the desired range. Coupled with high-frequency step-up transformers, this approach provides a flexible source of controlled, reproducible transient voltages for calibration and research purposes.

7.2 Test setup design

The transient generator was developed as a resonant RLC discharge circuit triggered by a high-speed switch. The core idea is to charge a capacitor to a set high voltage and then abruptly connect it to a resonant inductive network, producing a decaying sinusoidal voltage across the connected load.

The transient voltage generator follows a similar design philosophy to the DC voltage generator in terms of how it introduces high-frequency signals into the test circuit. Instead of utilizing an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) and broadband power amplifier to synthesize and inject the high-frequency component, the transient generator replaces these elements with the semiconductor-triggered RLC discharge circuit. The output of this RLC Generator, capable of producing controlled, damped sinusoidal transients, is then directly connected to the high-voltage, high-frequency transformer. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the conceptual schematic of the transient voltage generator.

The main generator is composed of the following components:

- **Capacitor Bank:** Selected to tune the oscillation frequency in combination with the circuit inductance. Various capacitance values (from tens of nF up to a few μF) were selected to target specific frequencies, e.g. using $\sim 0.25 \mu\text{F}$ for $\sim 95 \text{ kHz}$, $15 \mu\text{F}$ for $\sim 9 \text{ kHz}$.
- **Inductances:** A combination of dedicated inductors and the leakage inductance of the step-up transformer formed the resonant inductive element. Initial tests used $\sim 11 \mu\text{H}$ inductance yielding $\sim 90 \text{ kHz}$ oscillations with $\sim 0.255 \mu\text{F}$ capacitance. For lower frequencies, larger inductances or transformer windings were used, e.g. $\sim 35 \mu\text{H}$ for $\sim 20 \text{ kHz}$ range.
- **Switching Device:** A high-voltage MOSFET transistor was used to switch and connect the charged capacitor to the inductive circuit, discharging the capacitor into the resonant loop. The MOSFET provided controlled triggering of the transient and was tasked to withstand the peak current, tens to hundreds of amperes, during the discharge. The gate of the MOSFET was activated via a fiber optic trigger. The trigger pulses were generated using a function generator, allowing the triggering of the MOSFET to be synchronized with the zero-crossing or another selectable phase point of the 50 Hz voltage if necessary.
- **HV Supply to charge the RLC circuit capacitors:** A programmable DC source (Fluke 410B) was used for consistent charging up to $\sim 1.0\text{--}1.5 \text{ kV}$.
- **High Frequency Voltage Transformer:** The output of the resonant circuit was coupled to the measurement or test object through a transformer. This step was critical to achieve the desired 3 kV amplitude without exposing the MOSFET/capacitor to the full HV. Several transformer configurations were tested to cover the wide frequency span:
 - A 5:50 HFVT (high turns ratio $\sim 1:10$) was used for the lowest frequencies ($\sim 9\text{--}20 \text{ kHz}$) where a large voltage amplification was needed.

- A tunable ratio HFVT was used for mid and high frequencies up to 150 kHz. This HFVT allowed for flexible winding configuration: the primary winding could be selected with either one or two turns depending on the experimental requirements, while the secondary—being a toroidal-type transformer—enabled manual adjustment of the number of turns. This made it possible to increase or decrease the transformation ratio as needed by simply adding or removing turns from the secondary winding, which was especially useful for adapting the output to the required frequency range or voltage level.
- A high-voltage divider and high-speed oscilloscope were used to monitor the output waveform. The oscilloscope power supply was isolated from ground to prevent grounding issues.

Figure 27. Conceptual schematic of the Test Setup.

7.3 Test procedure

The test procedure consisted of the following steps until obtaining the full capability of generation for each frequency. All these tests were performed with an HVDC level of 25 kV.

1. Frequency Tuning: Small-signal tests were done to verify that the selected LC values produced the intended oscillation frequency. For example, with $L \approx 11 \mu\text{H}$ and $C \approx 0.255 \mu\text{F}$, the calculated frequency was 95 kHz, and the measured value was 88.5 kHz. Differences between the measured and calculated value are due to stray inductances and capacitance and the main capacitor tolerances. Similar checks were done for other capacitor values (0.1 μF for ~150 kHz, etc.).
2. Incremental Voltage Tests: The capacitor charge voltage was gradually raised and transients triggered to observe the waveform and look for distortion or saturation. The current through the MOSFET switch was also being monitored, so that it would not go above the rated current value.
3. Full-Scale Shots: Finally, full-energy shots were conducted. The capacitor was charged to around 1.0–1.1 kV (and up to ~1.5 kV in some cases) and the MOSFET triggered to generate the transient. The output voltage and current were recorded across the frequency bands.

Error! Reference source not found. shows views of the test setup for each HFVT.

Figure 28. View of the test setup. a) 5:50 ratio HFVT. b) Tunable ratio HFVT

7.4 Error! Reference source not found. Results

The voltage transient generator developed in this task successfully produced damped sinusoidal voltages across the target frequency spectrum. It achieved the 3 kV peak voltage goal at representative frequencies in the low, mid, and high ends of the range. Depending on the frequency range, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Low Band Frequency (9 - 18 kHz): Using the 5:50 HFVT and large capacitances, e.g. from 4 μF to 15 μF .
- Mid Band Frequency (20 - 60 kHz): Using the tunable ratio HFVT with a ratio from 1:8 to 1:11 and moderate capacitances, e.g. from 3 μF to 7.5 μF .
- High Band Frequency (60 - 150 kHz): Using the tunable ratio HFVT with a ratio of 1:4 and smaller capacitances, e.g. from 0.1 - 0.5 μF .

Table 5 shows the configuration parameters of the generator and the transient voltage results for each frequency and Figure 28 shows an example of a generated sinusoidal damped transient voltage.

Table 5. Generator parameters and test results.

Center frequency (kHz)	HFVT output ratio	LC circuit		Voltage transient V_{peak} (kV)	Current through the Mosfet I_{peak} (A)
		Inductance (μH)	Capacitance (μF)		
8.8	5:50	20	15	2.96	608
11.5	5:50	35	4.5	3.04	72.6
16.3	5:50	20	4	2.95	214
21.9	1:11	8	7.5	3.10	671
22.2	1:11	8	7.5	3.10	630
26.7	1:8	10	4	2.89	529
30.4	1:8	10	3	3.09	478
39.1	1:8	6	3	2.94	567
62.1	1:4	11	0.5	2.91	173
128.8	1:4	11	0.1	3.13	69

Figure 28. Example of a sinusoidal damped transient voltage.

7.5 Conclusion

The developed transient voltage generator successfully produced damped sinusoidal transients across the entire target frequency band, achieving peak voltages of about 3 kV. Different transformer ratios and LC combinations were used to cover the low (9–18 kHz), mid (20–60 kHz), and high (60–150 kHz) frequency ranges, with stable operation and consistent waveform quality. The results confirm that the generator can reliably reproduce realistic supraharmonic transients, making it a suitable tool for evaluating medium-voltage instrument transformers under transient overvoltage conditions.

8 General conclusion

This work has presented the design, development, and characterization of several complementary voltage generation systems aimed at reproducing realistic high-frequency in the range from 9 kHz to 150 kHz and transient conditions for the testing of medium-voltage instrument transformers. Four main types of generators were investigated:

- Parallel-connected AC generators (Chapter 2): designed to superimpose different frequency components by connecting generation paths in parallel. This configuration offers the advantage of reducing the stress on individual components while allowing independent control of each frequency band. It also improves stability and reduces unwanted interactions between low-frequency and high-frequency sources.
- Series-connected AC generators (Chapter 3): combining a high-voltage DC source with a high-frequency AC injection path. This architecture demonstrated the feasibility of superimposing harmonic components up to 150 kHz onto a DC voltage of tens of kilovolts. Its main advantage lies in its flexibility and modularity, allowing controlled harmonic injection while maintaining galvanic isolation and safe operation.
- Using a single transformer (Chapter 4): a simplified architecture that reduces system complexity and footprint. Its performance at high frequencies is good, it provides an effective solution for cases where compactness and reduced component count are important. Some parameters such as temperature and burden need to take it into account when developing this method.
- DC voltage generator with harmonic injection at ground potential (Chapter 5): an improved design where the high-frequency injection transformer is placed at ground level, simplifying insulation requirements and improving stability. This approach enabled harmonic voltages up to ~1 kVRMS superimposed on 50 kV DC, with robust operation across a wide frequency range. Its main advantage is the ease of implementation, higher efficiency, and reduced insulation stress compared to series-connected architectures.
- Transient voltage generator (Chapter 6): a resonant RLC-based system capable of producing damped sinusoidal oscillations in the 9–150 kHz range with amplitudes up to 3 kV. This generator is particularly suited for reproducing fast overvoltage transients representative of realistic supraharmmonic disturbances in MV networks. Its advantage is the ability to generate short, high-energy oscillations in a controlled and reproducible way, making it a valuable tool for stress testing and transient studies.
- The experimental campaign demonstrated that these generation systems can reliably cover a broad spectrum of test conditions, including steady-state supraharmonics and transient waveforms, while addressing key challenges such as transformer insulation, frequency response, and load effects. By adopting innovative solutions—such as ground-referenced injection, modular transformer configurations, and parallel coupling strategies—the project ensured safe operation, improved bandwidth, and enhanced waveform fidelity.
- Overall, the suite of generators developed in this work provides a versatile and reliable platform for advancing calibration and testing capabilities in the supraharmmonic domain. These tools not only support present-day requirements for evaluating instrument transformers under non-sinusoidal and transient conditions but also pave the way for future extensions to higher power levels, broader frequency ranges, and integration into standardized testing infrastructures.

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